

Ethics of Activating Investment Policy through Abu Yusuf's Book "Al-Kharaj"

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Abstract

This research aims to explore the ethics governing the activation of investment policy based on the principles established in Abu Yusuf's book *Al-Kharaj*. The research focuses on four main pillars: mastery of work, sincerity and piety, trustworthiness and prohibition of deceit, and the legitimacy of investment means. It examines how these principles can be applied in investment policy to achieve economic efficiency and social justice. The research concludes that these ethical principles remain relevant in the modern era and play a crucial role in fostering trust between individuals and institutions.

Keywords: Ethics, Investment, Policy, Abu Yusuf's Book "Al-Kharaj"

Introduction:

The book *Al-Kharaj* by Abu Yusuf is one of the most prominent jurisprudential works addressing economic and financial aspects in the Islamic state. It provides a legislative framework for organizing financial resources, land management, and taxation. This book reflects a comprehensive Islamic vision for economic policy, rooted in principles of justice, trustworthiness, and excellence. This research explores the ethics that should govern the activation of investment policy based on the principles outlined in *Al-Kharaj*, focusing on four main pillars: mastery of work, sincerity and piety, trustworthiness and prohibition of deceit, and the legitimacy of investment means.

Historical Background:

The book *Al-Kharaj* dates back to the Abbasid era, where Abu Yusuf served as the chief judge during the reign of Caliph Harun al-Rashid. It was written in response to the Caliph's request to establish a fair financial policy based on Islamic law. The book addresses issues such as land distribution, tax collection, and natural resource management, emphasizing that these processes must adhere to Islamic ethics. Thus, it provides a model for investment policy rooted in moral values, making it a significant reference for understanding how to implement economic policies ethically.

Section One: Mastery of Work

Mastery of work is the path to earning reward, attaining Allah's pleasure, and achieving excellence. In the prophetic tradition, the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) said: "*Indeed, Allah loves when one of you performs a task, he perfects it*".ⁱ

Mastery in work is the criterion that distinguishes the diligent from the negligent. While everyone performs tasks, the difference lies in the degree of mastery in their work. Consequently, an employer or ruler can identify those who excel and reward them, setting incentives to encourage others to follow their example.

Mastery of work also teaches people to strive for perfection in all aspects of life and refines their character. A person who masters their work strives for excellence and perfection in everything, achieving self-actualization.

For this reason, Judge Abu Yusuf urged the Caliph to master his work, citing a hadith in this regard. He said: "*Yazid ibn Sinan narrated to us from A'idh Allah ibn Idris, who said: Shaddad ibn Aws addressed the people, praising Allah and thanking Him, then said: 'I heard the Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) say: "Indeed, all good is in Paradise, and all evil is in Hellfire. Paradise is surrounded by hardships, and Hellfire is surrounded by desires. When a person is faced*

with hardship and endures it, he ascends to Paradise and becomes one of its people. When a person is faced with desire and indulges in it, he descends to Hellfire and becomes one of its people. So, work with truth for a day when nothing but truth will prevail; take your places in truth".ⁱⁱ

The key point in the hadith is the phrase "work with truth," which implies mastering work and performing it to the best of one's ability.

Section Two: Sincerity and Piety

Sincerity is one of the most important acts of the heart. It is the essence of faith and the distinction between monotheism and polytheism. No deed is accepted without sincerity. A Muslim must purify their intention in every action they perform so that Allah accepts it, whether they are a ruler or a subject, male or female. For Allah, the Exalted, does not accept any deed unless it is done sincerely for His sake. Allah has commanded this in numerous verses, *such as*: {Say, 'Indeed, I have been commanded to worship Allah, [being] sincere to Him in religion. And I have been commanded to be the first of the Muslims.' Say, 'Indeed, I fear, if I should disobey my Lord, the punishment of a tremendous Day.' Say, 'It is Allah I worship, sincere to Him in my religion}. (Quran 39:11-14). "And they were not commanded except to worship Allah, [being] sincere to Him in religion, inclining to truth, and to establish prayer and to give zakah. And that is the correct religion". Quran (98:5), "So worship Allah, [being] sincere to Him in religion. Unquestionably, for Allah is the pure religion". (Quran: 39: 2-3)

Sincerity is an essential trait for a Muslim, whether they are a ruler, worker, investor, or otherwise. A ruler must purify their intentions and fear Allah in governing their people, striving to achieve their worldly and spiritual interests without oppressing or tyrannizing them, for Allah does not love the oppressors. A worker must perfect their work because Allah commands excellence in work. Similarly, an investor must fear Allah in their investments, ensuring they only invest in what is lawful to earn Allah's reward.

Due to the importance of sincerity and piety in supporting investment policies in accordance with Islamic law, Imam Abu Yusuf paid great attention to reminding and advising the Caliph. He emphasized these two qualities in multiple instances, explaining their significance and the danger of neglecting them. He stated that success in both worlds belongs to those who are pious and sincere, and that anyone who acts in a way that incurs Allah's wrath will face severe punishment. Abu Yusuf said: *"O Commander of the Faithful, Allah—to whom all praise belongs—has entrusted you with a great matter: its reward is the greatest of rewards, and its punishment is the most severe of punishments... No structure built without piety will last long before Allah destroys it from its foundations, causing it to collapse upon its builder and those who supported it".ⁱⁱⁱ*

He also reminded the Caliph that piety is his most trustworthy guardian, saying:

"Be cautious, for caution lies in the heart, not on the tongue. Fear Allah, for piety is in being cautious, and whoever fears Allah, He will protect him".^{iv}

After all this, Abu Yusuf cited a hadith of the Prophet (peace be upon him) on this matter, in which the Prophet said: *"May Allah brighten the face of a person who hears my words and conveys them. Many carry knowledge but do not understand it, and many convey knowledge to those who understand it better. Three things ensure that a believer's heart remains free from malice: sincerity in deeds for Allah, sincere advice to Muslim rulers, and adhering to the Muslim community, for their supplication encompasses those behind them".^v*

Section Three: Trustworthiness and Prohibition of Deceit

Trustworthiness is a noble trait and, at the same time, a great responsibility. In Islam, it is the sister of honesty and its inseparable companion. Wherever honesty is found, trustworthiness is present, and wherever honesty is lost, trustworthiness is lost. No investment can achieve the objectives of Sharia unless the investor adheres to the principle of trustworthiness.

Trustworthiness is the capital of an investor and the cornerstone upon which the success of their investment depends. Those who are trusted by people in their dealings—whether in consumption or investment—find their goods in demand, their profits increasing, and their acceptance growing both with Allah and with people.

Numerous verses of the Quran and the traditions of the Prophet (peace be upon him) emphasize the importance of fulfilling trusts and avoiding betrayal. For example, Allah says:

{Indeed, we offered the Trust to the heavens and the earth and the mountains, but they declined to bear it and feared it. But man undertook it; indeed, he was unjust and ignorant.} (Quran 33:72).

Imam al-Tabari said: *"The Trust in this context refers to all the trusts in religion, as well as all the trusts between people, because the verse does not specify a particular type of trust, so the general meaning is more appropriate"*.^{vi}

Allah also says:

Indeed, Allah commands you to render trusts to their rightful owners... (Quran 4:58).

Imam al-Tabari, after citing the interpretations of the commentators, said:

"The most correct interpretation, in my view, is that this is a command from Allah to the rulers of the Muslims to fulfil the trusts to those under their authority, whether in public funds, rights, or matters entrusted to them, by judging with justice and dividing with fairness".^{vii}

Trustworthiness was among the advice Abu Yusuf gave to Caliph Harun al-Rashid. He guided him to preserve it, fear Allah, and not neglect the responsibility Allah had entrusted to him over his subjects. He reminded the Caliph that he would be held accountable before Allah for every small and large matter, warning him against injustice and oppression. He advised him on how to save himself from Allah's punishment on the Day when neither wealth nor children will benefit anyone, except those who come to Allah with a sound heart. He said: *"O Commander of the Faithful... Allah has entrusted you with them, made you responsible for them, and tested you with them... Do not neglect what Allah has entrusted to you regarding this nation and its people, for strength lies in acting with Allah's permission"*.^{viii}

He also said to him: *"The shepherds are accountable to their Lord for what they shepherd. So, establish justice in what Allah has entrusted to you, even if only for an hour of the day. The happiest shepherds before Allah on the Day of Judgment are those whose flock was happy with them. Do not deviate, lest your flock deviates with you. Beware of following desires and acting in anger"*.^{ix}

In another instance, he said: "I advise you, O Commander of the Faithful, to preserve what Allah has entrusted to you and to care for what He has made you responsible for. Do not look at it except with His perspective and for His sake. If you do not do so, the ease of guidance will become difficult for you, its path will become obscure, its signs will fade, and its vastness will narrow for you. You will begin to reject what you once accepted and accept what you once rejected. So, argue with yourself as one who seeks victory for it, not against it. For the negligent shepherd is responsible for what is lost under his care, even if he could have saved it with Allah's permission. If he neglects it, he loses it, and if he becomes preoccupied with other matters, destruction will come to him faster and harm him more. If he reforms, he will be the happiest and Allah will reward him manifold. Beware of neglecting your flock, lest their Lord demands their rights from you and you lose your reward due to your neglect. A structure is reinforced before it collapses. You will only have what you have done for those under your care, and you will be held accountable for what you neglected. Do not forget to fulfil the responsibilities of those under your care, for you will not be forgotten. Do not neglect them or what benefits them, for you will not be neglected".^x

Abu Yusuf did not stop at this advice alone. He also cited hadiths and narrations that emphasize preserving trustworthiness and prohibiting betrayal and deceit. For example: Abu Yusuf said: "Yahya ibn Sa'id narrated to me from al-Harith ibn Ziyad al-Himyari that Abu Dharr asked the Prophet (peace be upon him) for a position of authority. The Prophet said: 'You are weak, and it is a trust. On the Day of Judgment, it will be a source of disgrace and regret, except for those who take it with its rights and fulfill its responsibilities'".^{xi}

He also said:

Ghilan ibn Qays al-Hamdani narrated to me from Ubay ibn Malik, who said: 'Our elders among the companions of Muhammad (peace be upon him) commanded us not to curse our leaders, not to deceive them, not to disobey them, and to fear Allah and be patient'.^{xii}

Section Four: Legitimacy of Investment Means through the Book of Al-Kharaj

There is no doubt that investment, in the sense of developing and reviving the earth, is encouraged in Islam. The Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) emphasized this, and its legitimacy is confirmed by Quranic verses, prophetic traditions, and the practices of the Rightly Guided Caliphs. Imam Abu Yusuf relied on these texts in his book *Al-Kharaj*, and I will elaborate on the legitimacy of investment means.

First: The Quran

There are numerous texts in the Quran that indicate means of investment, including:

1- Commanding to Walk Through the Earth as a Means of Investment: Several verses command walking through the earth to seek the sustenance that Allah has spread across its vast expanse. This is evident in the divine command: **{It is He who made the earth tame for you - so walk among its slopes and eat of His provision - and to Him is the resurrection.}** (Al-Mulk: 15). This verse indicates the obligation to invest in the earth and the means to achieve it.

Walking through the earth is commanded to uncover its hidden treasures and enjoy them in life. Thus, walking is essentially a means to investment, as it leads to reaping the blessings and resources Allah has placed in the earth for humanity to benefit from through various means such as agriculture, industry, and trade.

Ibn Jarir al-Tabari, after citing the interpretations of the commentators, said:

"The most correct interpretation, in my view, is that it means: walk through its regions and sides, as its regions are akin to the shoulders of a person, which are part of their limbs. His saying: (and eat of His provision) means: eat from the sustenance Allah has provided for you from the earth's regions, (and to Him is the resurrection) means: to Allah is your return from your graves".^{xiii}

2- Commanding to Travel Through the Earth as a Means of Investment:

Numerous texts from the Quran and Sunnah encourage traveling through the earth in search of Allah's bounty and sustenance. Upon examining these texts and their implications, one finds that traveling through the earth is an obligation and a means of investment, as attaining Allah's bounty and sustenance depends on it.

Allah says:

Indeed, your Lord knows that you stand [in prayer] for less than two-thirds of the night or half of it or a third of it, and [so do] a group of those with you. And Allah determines [the extent of] the night and the day. He has known that you [Muslims] will not be able to do it and has turned to you in forgiveness, so recite what is easy [for you] of the Quran. He has known that there will be among you those who are ill and others traveling throughout the land seeking Allah's bounty... (Al-Muzzammil: 20).

Traveling through the earth here refers to seeking livelihood. Ibn Jarir, in interpreting {and others traveling through the land}, said: *"It means traveling in search of Allah's bounty through trade, as they travelled seeking livelihood, which weakened them and made them unable to stand in prayer at night".^{xiv}*

3- Commanding the Development of the Earth and Human Stewardship as the Basis for Its

Prosperity: Developing the earth in accordance with Allah's divine will is a necessary aspect of human stewardship and a fundamental task assigned to humanity. Allah says:

And to Thamud [We sent] their brother Salih. He said, 'O my people, worship Allah; you have no deity other than Him. He produced you from the earth and settled you in it, so ask forgiveness of Him and then repent to Him. Indeed, my Lord is near and responsive.' (Hud: 61).

This verse commands the duty of developing and cultivating the earth in accordance with Allah's divine will. Ibn Jarir said: *"(And settled you in it), meaning: He made you its inhabitants, so the meaning is: He settled you in it during your lifetime".^{xv}*

Second: The Prophetic Sunnah

1- Commanding to Plant Trees and Emphasizing Agriculture as a Means of Investment:

- It is narrated in an authentic hadith that the Prophet (peace be upon him) said: *"There is no Muslim who plants a tree or sows a crop, and a bird, person, or animal eats from it, except that it is considered a charity for him".^{xvi}*
- The hadith of Anas states: *"If the Hour is about to be established and one of you has a sapling in his hand, if he can plant it before the Hour is established, let him plant it".^{xvii}*

2- Mandating Trade with Orphan's Wealth as an Emphasis on Investment:

Narrated by Amr ibn Shu'ayb, from his father, from his grandfather, that the Prophet (peace be upon him) said: *"Whoever is entrusted with an orphan's wealth should trade with it and not leave it idle until it is consumed by charity".^{xviii}*

This hadith encourages trade and work as important means of investment.

Third: The Practices of the Rightly Guided Caliphs Regarding Investment

I conclude this research with a remarkable stance of Umar ibn al-Khattab (may Allah be pleased with him), who ordered the reclaiming of land left idle for more than three years, saying: *"Whoever revives dead land, it belongs to him, and no one has the right to monopolize it after three years".^{xix}*

Similarly, when he saw Bilal ibn al-Harith, whom the Prophet (peace be upon him) had granted land in Al-Aqiq, neglecting to invest in it, he said to him: *"The Messenger of Allah (peace be upon him) did not grant you this land to withhold it from people; he granted it to you so that you would work it..."*.^{xx}

These texts clearly indicate the investment policies followed during the era of the Rightly Guided Caliphs and how they established foundations to ensure the effectiveness of these investment policies and their fruitful outcomes.

Results:

1. The ethical principles outlined in *Al-Kharaj* remain relevant in the modern era and can be applied to achieve economic efficiency and social justice.
2. Mastery of work enhances productivity and reduces costs, benefiting individuals and institutions.
3. Sincerity and piety ensure integrity and transparency in financial dealings, fostering trust between parties.
4. Trustworthiness and the prohibition of deceit contribute to building cohesive societies based on trust and cooperation.

Recommendations:

1. **For Governments:** Adopt investment policies based on Islamic ethical principles, such as justice, trustworthiness, and excellence.
2. **For Educational Institutions:** Incorporate Islamic ethical principles into curricula to raise awareness of the importance of ethics in practical life.
3. **For Investors:** Adhere to Sharia-compliant standards in investment, avoiding projects that harm society or the environment.
4. **For Researchers:** Conduct further studies on the application of Islamic ethical principles in economic and financial fields.

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